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Radiation Risk Assessment from Background Radiation Exposures in Selected Private Diagnostic Centers in River State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Radiation has been found to be beneficial on one hand and harmful on the other hand and is encountered in everyday activities in various forms and different intensities. Some of the harmful effects are: cancer, cataract, gene mutation destruction of bones and blood cells and it can cause the death of an individual.

This work therefore aimed at investigating the indoor and outdoor background radiation risk assessment of three different private diagnostic centers in Port-Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria using a handheld Radiation Alert Inspector survey meter. More than twenty sampling points were randomly selected within each diagnostic facility and the results obtained showed that for facility A, The background ionizing radiation exposure rate (indoor and outdoor) measured ranged from 0.04 to 0.12 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.084 \pm 0.023 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$, 0.04 to 0.13 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.086 \pm 0.034 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility A, 0.07 to 0.045 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.128 \pm 0.005 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$, 0.07 to 0.15 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.133 \pm 0.028 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility B, 0.08 to 0.19 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.106 \pm 0.027 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ and 0.05 to 0.14 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.096 \pm 0.024 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility C respectively. It shows that the equivalent dose rate levels in the selected diagnostic centers are low compared with the data obtained in the previous studies in River State Government hospitals but in line with the study carried out in some hospitals in other states in Nigeria. Hence, the study showed that the mean equivalent dose rate levels are within the international commission on radiological protection's standard permissible limits. The mean (AEDE) annual effective dose equivalent (indoor and outdoor) for all the selected diagnostic facilities within the recommended permissible limits of 1.00 mSv/yr for the general public. Base on the aforementioned findings, it was deduced that radiation levels are within the permissible radiation limit as stipulated by the ICRP of 1.0 mSv/y and UNSCEAR of 2.4 mSv/yr and thus, radiologically safe.

Keywords: Indoor and Outdoor, Background Radiation, Equivalent Dose, Effective Dose, Radiation Alert meter.

INTRODUCTION

It is worthy of note that there is natural radiation called background radiation everywhere in the environment (cosmic rays), from naturally occurring radioactive materials and other living things (HPSP, 2016). Background ionizing radiation was originally attributed to natural sources. This has over the years

increased due to human activities and has been of great concern because of the known effects of exposure to higher doses (Ononugbo & Mgbemere, 2016), which are characterized with half-lives comparable to the age of the earth (Sharma *et al.*, 2017) and are present everywhere in the environment; in rocks, soil, water, sediments, foods and including the human body itself (UNSCEAR, 2008). The use of radiation sources in medical diagnosis and therapy, nuclear weapons, nuclear power plants, fertilizers production, research institutions as well as in consumers' products have contributed to increase in background radiation exposure and doses

The major sources of ionizing radiation in our environment are cosmogenic, anthropogenic and primordial sources (Omogunloye *et al.*, 2021). Of all these sources, the primordial radiation sources are of the major concern, since the radiation from cosmogenic and anthropogenic sources are negligible. Primordial radiation levels are dependent on local geological conditions and geographical location of the area (Akortia *et al.*, 2021). Ionizing radiation can be beneficial and harmful, depending on the levels of exposure. When the level of exposure to ionizing radiation exceeds certain limits within the environment, it becomes harmful and could cause certain health disorders such as acute leukemia, lung cancer, pancreas, hepatic, skin and kidney cancers, cataracts, and sterility (Vaiserman *et al.*, 2018). To safeguard the health of the public from the adverse effects of exposure to background ionizing radiation (BIR), it has become necessary to survey the BIR levels within the environment.

Recently, there were studies that have been directed towards investigating BIR levels in various areas. In Nigeria, studies have been conducted in various part of the country to measure the natural background radiation level around private and government hospitals. It was reported that the indoor equivalent dose of 2.063 mSvyr^{-1} was recorded at Skane Radiological centre Jos, while the outdoor of the same diagnostic center recorded 1.84 mSvyr^{-1} (Jwanbot *et al.*, 2012). In Plateau State Specialist hospital, indoor equivalent dose of radiation was 2.44 mSvyr^{-1} and outdoor radiation dose equivalent was 2.002 mSvyr^{-1} (Jwanbot *et al.*, 2012). Measurement of indoor and outdoor background ionising radiation levels of Kwali General Hospital, Abuja (James *et al.*; 2015) recorded the average annual equivalent dose rate of $0.750 \pm 0.020 \text{ mSv/y}$ and $0.189 \pm 0.005 \text{ mSv/y}$ for indoor and outdoor measurements respectively. Measurement of background ionizing radiation level at Braithwaite Memorial specialist hospital, Port Harcourt was done. Indoor annual equivalent dose ranged from $0.14 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{Svhr}^{-1}$ to $0.16 \pm 0.01 \mu\text{Svhr}^{-1}$ (Okoye and Avwiri, 2013). Indoor and outdoor effective doses from background ionizing radiation in Private Medical Diagnostic Centers in Bori, Rivers State (Ononugbo, *et al.*; 2015). Assessment of Radiation Risk from Background Radiation Exposures in Selected Hospitals within Makurdi Metropolis, North-Central, Nigeria (Omogunloye *et al.*; 2021) recorded background ionizing radiation exposure rate (indoor and outdoor) ranged from 0.0014 to 0.0019 mRhr^{-1} with average value 0.0017 mRhr^{-1} , 0.0015 to 0.0024 mRhr^{-1} with average value 0.0019 mRhr^{-1} , 0.0013 to 0.0025 mRhr^{-1} with average value 0.0018 mRhr^{-1} and 0.0012 to 0.0024 mRhr^{-1} with average value 0.0018 mRhr^{-1} .

The present work aims at evaluating the indoor and outdoor effective dose of background radiation in three different private diagnostic centers, in Port-Harcourt in order to compare the radiological burden of private and government hospitals in River State and some recently studied hospitals in Nigeria. The result of this survey will serve as baseline data for future research.

3. Study area

The study locations were the radiology units of three different hospitals namely, Image Diagnostic Center, Analytic Diagnostic Center and Intercontinental Diagnostics Center. The diagnostics Centers are private radio-diagnostic centers having 16, 64 and 128 slices computed tomography scan machines. The centers were located in Port Harcourt metropolis in Port Harcourt City Local Government Council and located at $N4^{\circ}49'54.08176$, $E6^{\circ}59'42.814$; $N4^{\circ}49' .133$ ", $E6^{\circ} 59' .883$ " and $N4^{\circ} 49' 28.125$ ", $E7^{\circ} 0' 31.0768$ " respectively.

Port Harcourt is the capital city of Rivers State, Nigeria. Port Harcourt having approximately a total area of 664 sqkm with cosmopolitan area of 934 sqkm and can be accessed and linked to the world over by air,

sea, land and with an altitude of 1.00–3.00m above the sea level (Ihuah & Kakulu, 2016; Chijioko-Nwauche et al., 2020).

Port Harcourt metropolis lies between longitudes 6°55' and 7°10' East of the Greenwich meridian and latitudes 4°40' and 4°55' north of the equator. The city is located within Niger Delta and along the bonny River (Ihu& Kakulu, 2016). The city has an estimated population of 1,865,000 inhabitants according to Ihuah and Kakulu (2016).

Facilities are private medical facilities that operate basically diagnostic services including medical laboratory and radio-diagnosis. The radio-diagnostic services ranges from conventional radiography, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), computed tomography etc.

Map of Port Harcourt showing Study Centers

4. MATERIALS AND METHOD

Radiation Alert Inspector survey meter was the instrument used to perform the environmental radiation survey. The Radiation alert meter is a general-purpose survey meter that measures alpha, beta, gamma and x-ray radiation. It has proven to be useful in medical, nuclear, mining, metal scrap and laundry industries. The Radiation alert radiation meter sets a new standard in portable Geiger counter performances and

functionality. It is calibrated across a wide scale (0.01 up to 1000.00 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$). Global Positioning System (GPS) was used to measure the geographical coordinates of the sampling points.

More than twenty sampling points were randomly selected within each diagnostic facility center. Outdoor background radiation readings were taken around the facility premises away from the building. Indoor measurements were done inside the diagnostic center's rooms and corridors. Measurement at each facility was performed by holding the Rad-alert at 1m above to ground surface. Each measurement was taken three times and the average taken to represent the value for background radiation level of the hospital and standard deviations calculated to account for the errors in the measurement.

5. Estimation of radiological parameters Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE)

The annual effective dose equivalent in millisievert per year (mSv/yr) was calculated using the relationship in Equation 1.0 and 2.0 for outdoor and indoor exposure rates respectively ((Oladele & Arogunjo, 2018).

$$\text{AEDE (Outdoor) Sv/yr} = \text{AD (nGy/h)} \times 8760\text{h} \times 0.7\text{Sv/Gy} \times 0.25 \times 10^{-3} \quad 1.0$$

$$\text{AEDE (Indoor) Sv/yr} = \text{AD (nGy/h)} \times 8760\text{h} \times 0.7\text{Sv/Gy} \times 0.8 \times 10^{-3} \quad 2.0$$

Where:

AD is the absorbed dose from background exposure rate

0.7Sv/Gy is the dose conversion factor

6. Results

Tables 1, 2,3,4,5 and 6 present the indoor and outdoor radiation exposure rates and the estimated radiological risk of facility A, B and C respectively. The tables also show the absorbed dose from the background exposure, the Annual Effective Dose Equivalent (AEDE) and the Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR) from the background exposure rate obtained by using equations (1) and (2) of both indoor and outdoor measurements.

1. The environmental background radiation levels in diagnostic facilities measured were both indoors and outdoors to assess the associated radiological risk. The background ionizing radiation exposure rate (indoor and outdoor) measured for the selected diagnostic facilities A, B and C ranges from 0.04 to 0.12 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.084 \pm 0.023 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$, 0.04 to 0.13 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.086 \pm 0.034 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility A, 0.07 to 0.045 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average value $0.101 \pm 0.022 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$, 0.07 to 0.15 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.113 \pm 0.028 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility B, 0.08 to 0.19 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.106 \pm 0.027 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ and 0.05 to 0.14 $\mu\text{Sv/hr}$ with average $0.096 \pm 0.024 \mu\text{Sv/hr}$ for facility C respectively. The highest exposure rate was recorded for the indoor at the facility B; this could be due to the presence of radiation sources (x-ray machines and other equipment). Routine equipment maintenance (i.e. X-ray machine & CT scanner) and compliance with operational regulation be implemented in the diagnostic center. The measured background ionizing radiation exposure in all the selected diagnostic facilities are lower than the recommended ICRP safe levels permissible limit of 0.013 mR/hr. The low background ionizing radiation exposure rate reported for the studied diagnostic centers implies non-radiological contamination, thereby are radiologically safe and healthy for the general public of the study area.

2. The absorbed dose rate measures the amount of radiation deposited per unit time, so it is crucial in radiation risk analysis. To avoid any somatic, epidemiological, or radiological health effects, the International Commission on Radiological Protection proposed and set the maximum permissible level for non-radiation workers and the general public at 1.0 mSvyr^{-1}

For the selected diagnostic center A, B and C, the estimated radiation absorbed dose rate (indoor) ranged from 34.80 to 95.70 nGyhr^{-1} with a mean value of $73.08 \pm 19.99 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$, 60.90 to 121.80 nGyhr^{-1} with a mean value of $88.24 \pm 18.85 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$, 69.60 to 165.30 nGyhr^{-1} with a mean value of $92.22 \pm 23.49 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$ while the estimated average radiation absorbed dose rates (outdoor) are $74.82 \pm 29.58 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$, $98.6 \pm 24.36 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$ and $83.52 \pm 20.88 \text{ nGyhr}^{-1}$ respectively. These dose rates arising from background ionizing radiation exposure in the studied locations are far higher than the recorded world weighted

average of 59.00 nGyhr^{-1} ; and recommended safe limit of 84.0 nGyhr^{-1} . Hence, exposure of the public to these radiations may pose significant health hazard and therefore regular and periodic monitoring of the background ionizing radiation level should be carried out to assess the health risk of staff, patients and the public. It is also recommended that routine equipment maintenance (i.e. X-ray machine & CT scanner) and compliance with operational regulation be implemented in all the selected diagnostic centers

3. The AEDE indoor takes place within a building and evaluates the radiation dangers posed by building materials, while AEDE outdoor involves considering the absorbed dose emitted from radionuclides in the environment.

For the selected diagnostic centers A, B and C, the calculated annual effective dose equivalent (indoor) ranges from 0.043 to 0.139 mSv/yr with an average value of $0.090 \pm 0.025 \text{ mSv/yr}$, 0.075 to 0.128 mSv/yr with average $0.108 \pm 0.003 \text{ mSv/yr}$, 0.075 to 0.203 mSv/yr with $0.113 \pm 0.029 \text{ mSv/yr}$ respectively while the calculated average annual effective dose equivalent (outdoor) are $0.092 \pm 0.036 \text{ mSv/yr}$, $0.121 \pm 0.030 \text{ mSv/yr}$, and $0.102 \pm 0.026 \text{ mSv/yr}$, respectively. The calculated indoor and outdoor annual effective dose equivalent in all the selected diagnostic centers is lower than the ICRP and UNSCEAR recommended permissible limits of 1.0 mSv/yr for the general public.

4. Excess Lifetime Cancer Risk (ELCR)

This is concerned with the likelihood of developing cancer throughout a lifetime for a particular degree of exposure. It is expressed as a number representing the number of cancers expected in a specific number of people after exposure to a carcinogen at a particular dose. It's worth mentioning that an increase in the ELCR leads to a corresponding increase in the risk of developing breast, prostate, or even blood cancer. Excess lifetime cancer risk (ELCR) is determined using equation (4) below.

$$\text{ELCR} = \text{AEDE} \times \text{DL} \times \text{RF} \quad (4)$$

where AEDE is the Annual Equivalent Dose Equivalent, DL is the average duration of life (estimated to 70 years) and RF is the Risk Factor (Sv^{-1}), i.e., fatal cancer risk per Sievert. For stochastic effects, ICRP uses RF as 0.05 for the public.

The calculated values for the indoor ELCR of the selected diagnostic centers A, B and C ranges from 0.15×10^{-3} to 0.486×10^{-3} with a mean value $0.314 \pm 0.086 \times 10^{-3}$, 0.262 to 0.486×10^{-3} with average $0.379 \pm 0.081 \times 10^{-3}$, 0.299 to 0.710×10^{-3} with average $0.396 \pm 0.101 \times 10^{-3}$ respectively while the calculated average values for the outdoor ELCR of the selected diagnostic centers A, B and C are $0.321 \pm 0.127 \times 10^{-3}$, $0.423 \pm 0.104 \times 10^{-3}$ and $0.358 \pm 0.089 \times 10^{-3}$ respectively. The mean indoor and outdoor ELCR values obtained are higher than the worldwide average value of 0.29×10^{-3} for all the selected diagnostic centers. These higher result for the indoor and outdoor excess lifetime cancer risk for all the selected diagnostic centers suggests that residents who intend to spend their entire lives in the area are at risk of developing cancer.

Table 1: Indoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Image Diagnostic Center (IM) Facility A

Location	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
IM1	6.995222	4.831700	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM2	6.995222	4.831689	0.09	78.30	0.096	0.336
IM3	6.995219	4.831689	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM4	6.995225	4.831675	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IM5	6.995222	4.831675	0.09	78.30	0.096	0.336
IM6	6.995225	4.831686	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IM7	6.995222	4.831692	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM8	6.995222	4.831689	0.06	52.20	0.064	0.224
IM9	6.995222	4.831700	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IM10	6.995222	4.831692	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IM11	6.995222	4.831708	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM12	6.995222	4.831700	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IM13	6.995222	4.831700	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM14	6.995222	4.831700	0.09	78.30	0.096	0.336
IM15	6.995225	4.831700	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM16	6.995222	4.831675	0.04	34.80	0.043	0.150
IM17	6.995222	4.831714	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IM18	6.995222	4.831692	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IM19	6.995208	4.831714	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM20	6.995222	4.831717	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM21	6.995222	4.831708	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IM22	6.995222	4.831733	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
Mean			0.084±0.023	73.08±19.99	0.090±0.025	0.314±0.086

Table 2: Outdoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Image Diagnostic Center (IM) Facility A

Location	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
IM1	6.995222	4.831750	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IM2	6.995203	4.831781	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IM3	6.995197	4.831817	0.09	78.30	0.096	0.336
IM4	6.995222	4.831708	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IM5	6.995225	4.831675	0.008	6.96	0.009	0.030
IM6	6.995222	4.831678	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IM7	6.995222	4.831678	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IM8	6.995222	4.831667	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM9	6.995194	4.831889	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM10	6.995206	4.831806	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IM11	6.995203	4.831806	0.04	34.80	0.043	0.150
IM12	6.995206	4.831806	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IM13	6.995222	4.831711	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM14	6.995200	4.831689	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IM15	6.995228	4.831764	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IM16	6.995222	4.831717	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IM17	6.995311	4.831700	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IM18	6.995289	4.831669	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM19	6.995389	4.831639	0.15	130.50	0.160	0.560
IM20	6.995339	4.831583	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IM21	6.995336	4.831636	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IM22	6.995278	4.831717	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
Mean			0.086±0.034	74.82±29.58	0.092±0.036	0.321±0.127

Table 3: Indoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Analytic Diagnostic Center (AD) Facility B

S/N	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
AD1	6.997778	4.818889	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD2	7.224167	4.853611	0.14	121.8	0.149	0.523
AD3	7.228611	4.858333	0.13	113.1	0.139	0.486
AD4	7.228611	4.853611	0.13	113.1	0.139	0.486
AD5	7.228611	4.858333	0.07	60.9	0.074	0.262
AD6	7.228611	4.858333	0.12	104.4	0.128	0.448
AD7	7.224167	4.853611	0.07	60.9	0.075	0.262
AD8	7.228611	4.858333	0.07	60.9	0.075	0.262
AD9	7.224167	4.853611	0.10	87.0	0.107	0.374
AD10	7.224167	4.853611	0.10	87.0	0.107	0.374
AD11	7.224167	4.853611	0.07	60.9	0.075	0.262
AD12	7.224167	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD13	7.224167	4.853611	0.09	78.3	0.096	0.336
AD14	7.224167	4.853611	0.08	69.6	0.085	0.299
AD15	7.224167	4.853611	0.12	104.4	0.128	0.448
AD16	7.224167	4.853611	0.07	60.9	0.075	0.262
AD17	7.228611	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD18	7.229722	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD19	7.224167	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD20	7.224167	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD21	7.224167	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
	Mean		0.101±0.022	88.24±18.85	0.108±0.023	0.379±0.081

Table 4: Outdoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Analytic Diagnostic Center (AD) FacilityB

SN	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
AD1	7.228611	4.853611	0.15	130.5	0.160	0.560
AD2	7.228611	4.853611	0.09	78.3	0.096	0.336
AD3	7.228611	4.853611	0.10	87.0	0.107	0.374
AD4	7.228611	4.853611	0.08	69.6	0.085	0.299
AD5	7.224167	4.854167	0.14	121.8	0.149	0.523
AD6	7.228611	4.853611	0.13	113.1	0.139	0.486
AD7	7.228611	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD8	7.228611	4.853611	0.13	113.1	0.139	0.486
AD9	7.228611	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD10	7.228611	4.853611	0.09	78.3	0.096	0.336
AD11	7.228611	4.858333	0.08	69.6	0.085	0.299
AD12	7.224167	4.853611	0.13	113.1	0.139	0.486
AD13	7.228611	4.853611	0.08	69.6	0.085	0.299
AD14	7.222778	4.853611	0.07	60.9	0.075	0.262
AD15	7.224167	4.853611	0.09	78.3	0.096	0.336
AD16	7.224167	4.853611	0.16	139.2	0.171	0.598
AD17	7.224167	4.853611	0.10	87.0	0.107	0.374
AD18	7.224167	4.853611	0.11	95.7	0.117	0.411
AD19	7.224167	4.853611	0.17	147.9	0.181	0.635
AD20	7.224167	4.853611	0.14	121.8	0.149	0.523
AD21	7.224167	4.853611	0.12	104.4	0.128	0.448
	Mean		0.113±0.028	98.6±24.36	0.121±0.030	0.423±0.104

Table 5: Indoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Intercontinental Diagnostic Center (IDC) Facility C

SN	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
IDC1	7.015404	4.819608	0.14	121.80	0.149	0.523
IDC2	7.010703	4.824503	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC3	7.007343	4.82411	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IDC4	7.011461	4.826114	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IDC5	7.011039	4.825925	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC6	7.01003	4.826089	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IDC7	7.009451	4.825992	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC8	7.009567	4.8254	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC9	7.010061	4.825547	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC10	7.011456	4.826356	0.19	165.30	0.203	0.710
IDC11	7.010028	4.823728	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IDC12	7.008903	4.824069	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC13	7.009086	4.824251	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC14	7.008633	4.824564	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IDC15	7.008678	4.824511	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC16	7.009083	4.824428	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC17	7.009056	4.824119	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC18	7.007342	4.823553	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC19	7.006664	4.824069	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC20	7.009603	4.824222	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC21	7.009222	4.82405	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IDC22	7.009	4.824208	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
Mean			0.106±0.027	92.22±23.49	0.113±0.029	0.396±0.101

Table 6: Outdoor Radiation Exposure Rate of Intercontinental Diagnostic Center (IDC) Facility C

SN	Longitude (DD)	Latitude (DD)	EXPOSURE ($\mu\text{Sv/hr}$)	Absorbed Dose (nGyh^{-1})	AEDE (mSvy^{-1})	ELCR ($\times 10^{-3}$)
IDC1	7.009458	4.824881	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IDC2	7.009475	4.824894	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC3	7.009461	4.824886	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC4	7.009450	4.824883	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IDC5	7.009639	4.825381	0.05	43.50	0.053	0.187
IDC6	7.009661	4.825422	0.07	60.90	0.075	0.262
IDC7	7.009786	4.825383	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC8	7.009792	4.825017	0.09	78.30	0.096	0.336
IDC9	7.009778	4.825028	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IDC10	7.008356	4.825022	0.14	121.80	0.149	0.523
IDC11	7.009583	4.825025	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IDC12	7.009503	4.824069	0.13	113.10	0.139	0.486
IDC13	7.009614	4.824251	0.12	104.40	0.128	0.448
IDC14	7.009592	4.825275	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC15	7.009519	4.825403	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IDC16	7.009544	4.825422	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC17	7.009547	4.825392	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC18	7.009694	4.825492	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC19	7.009714	4.825508	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
IDC20	7.009756	4.825569	0.10	87.00	0.107	0.374
IDC21	7.009686	5.697500	0.11	95.70	0.117	0.411
IDC22	7.009772	4.825478	0.08	69.60	0.085	0.299
Mean			0.096\pm0.024	83.52\pm20.88	0.102\pm0.026	0.358\pm0.089

Fig. 2: GIS map of the radiation levels of the diagnostic centers studied

Fig. 3: Radiation map of Image Diagnostic centers

Fig.4: Radiation contour map for Analytical Diagnostics

Fig.5: Radiation contour map for intercontinental diagnostic center

CONCLUSION

The analysis found from the study show that the mean equivalent dose rate levels are within the international commission on radiological protection's standard acceptable limits (ICRP). The study showed that the mean equivalent dose rate levels in all the selected diagnostic centers are within the standard permissible limits set by the international commission on radiological protection. The mean indoor and outdoor annual effective dose equivalent for all the selected hospitals is within ICRP and UNSCEAR recommended permissible limits of 1.0 mSv/yr for the general public

RECOMMENDATION

Based on the findings of this study, it is recommended that measures be put in place at these selected private diagnostic centers through regular workplace monitoring and quality control of radiation facilities to ensure that the acceptable limit is not exceeded. These facilities radiation safety officers should ensure that staff uses protective devices and dosimeters for proper personnel monitoring.

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